

A conference paper on
Review of some Open Source Security tools for Intrusion Detection
and Prevention in a Cloud Computing Environment: A Panacea for
Economic Recession.

By

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Abstract

Security have become an issue ever since the birth of cloud computing. Cloud computing like every computer network has security vulnerabilities. A network intrusion is any unauthorized activity on a computer network by an attacker. Intrusion detection system proffers a layer of defence, monitoring network traffic for suspicious predefined activities / pattern and alerting network administrators when suspicious traffic is detected. This paper seeks to address these vulnerabilities and reviews some open source tools that can be implemented to help secure the cloud computing environment. Open source tools that are reviewed include Snort, Bro, Suricata, Open WIPS and Security Onion.

Keywords: *Cloud computing, Intrusion Detection, Intrusion Prevention, Visualization, Iaas, Paas, Saas, Security tools, Snort, Bro, Suricata, Open WIPS and Security Onion.*

1.0 Introduction

The concept of cloud computing was first conceived over 40 years ago as the virtualization of resources to allow users access to significant computing power and resources. The term virtual comes from the telecommunications concept of a virtual private network (VPN). VPNs were developed to provide secure data and voice channels. Foster et al. (2008) defined cloud computing as, “a large-scale distributed computing paradigm that is driven by economies of scale, in which a pool of abstracted, virtualized, dynamically-scalable, managed computing power, storage, platforms, and services are delivered on demand to external customers over the Internet.”

Cloud computing is a large-scale distributed computing paradigm. It is a collection of sources in order to enable resource sharing in terms of scalability, managed computing services that are delivered on demand over the network. Its users need not to buy infrastructure, software, resources, as a result saving a large amount of expenditure. Cloud basically provides services through a third party. The third party provides services and resources on rent and users pay per use. This will save a lot of money and provides a greater flexibility to move from one service to another service. (Hisham et al, 2012).

Furthermore, Cloud computing services are delivered on demand and pay-per-use via internet web browser protocols (HTTP and HTTPS). They are configured dynamically for service delivery based on contractual agreements between cloud service provider and users (tenants). Corporations, governments and academic institutions are actively considering the adoption of cloud computing services to lower costs, improve performance, increase storage capacity, provide interoperability, and reduce power consumption (green IT).

Consequently, Cloud computing is a collection of sources in order to enable resource sharing in terms of scalability, managed computing services that are delivered on demand over the network. The cloud computing definition of NIST includes five essential features, three service models and four deployment models. The five essential features are resource pooling, broad network access, rapid elasticity and scalability, metered services (pay per use), on demand service. The three service models are Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), Software as a Service (SaaS); the four deployment models are community cloud, public cloud, private cloud and hybrid cloud. In a cloud computing environment, each of these models has their own significant services different from each other. (Peter & Grance, 2011).

Figure 1 - NIST Visual Model of Cloud Computing Definition [CSA11]

Fig. 1.1 Models of cloud computing

Cloud computing is emerging day by day. People are using its services very frequently and they don't have any other alternative for its services. But users are unaware about the security and privacy concerns in a cloud environment. Since cloud computing is distributed in nature, supports multi-user and multi-domain platform, it is more prone to security threats. Security threats can be in terms of intrusion prospects and DDoS attacks. Organizations need to provide firewalls, intrusion detection and prevention techniques, authentication, encryption and other powerful hardware and software protection to secure the stored data. Attackers try to find loopholes for breaking security. Attacks that originate from internal sources are called internal attacks. It includes unauthorized access of internal user. Attacks that originates from external sources are called external attacks

2.0 Review of Relevant Literatures

In this section, relevant literatures on threats to cloud computing environment will be x-rayed. Intrusion Detection Systems (IDSs) and Intrusion Prevention Systems (IPSs) are considered.

In 2009, the International Data Corporation (IDC), a leading market research and advisory organization, conducted a survey of more than 260 IT executives and managers to gather their opinions and concerns regarding cloud computing. Their report indicated that security is the top priority, as shown in Figure 2 below. The concern is that critical IT resources and information in cloud systems might be vulnerable to cyber-attacks or unauthorized access. The primary security concerns with cloud environments pertain to security, availability and performance. Many attacks are designed to block users from accessing services and providers from delivering services, i.e., denial of service. Service providers may face significant penalties due to their inability to deliver services to customers in accordance with regulatory requirements and Service Level Agreements (SLA).

Fig 2.1 Challenges / issues of cloud / on-demand model.

Traditional network security measures like firewall are better to stop many outsider attacks but attacks from within the network as well as some complicated outsider attacks (e.g. DoS and DDoS) can't be tackled effectively by using such mechanisms. This is the scenario where intrusion detection systems (IDS) come into play. The role of IDS in the security of cloud is very important since it acts as additional preventive layer of security and apart from detecting only known attacks, it can detect variants of many known attacks and unknown attacks. (Buecker, 2009)

An intrusion is defined as an attempt to compromise the Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability (CIA) or to bypass the security mechanisms of a computer or network. Intrusions may be triggered

by attackers trying to access the cloud resources through the Internet, legitimate users trying to obtain privileges not given to them formally, and privileged users who misuse their rights to access resources. (Frank, 2013). Intrusion detection is the process of monitoring the events in a computer system or network and analysing them for signs of intrusions. Intrusion detection system could be software, hardware or a combination of both for automating the process of intrusion detection. It captures data from the system or network under observation and notifies network manager by mailing or logging the intrusion event. However, the alerts generated by IDS are not always relevant to actual intrusion due to false negatives and false positives which affect the performance of IDS.

2.1 INTRUSIONS TO CLOUD SYSTEMS

This section illustrates several common attacks (intrusions), which causes availability, confidentiality and integrity issues to Cloud resources and services.

2.1.1. Insider attack

The person who could access the whole information system with privileged authority are defined as *insider*. Insider attacks are organized and performed by these individuals to destroy or manipulate the knowledge about system or providers and include every kind of attacks which can possibly be executed from inside. Authorized Cloud users may attempt to misuse unauthorized privileges. Insiders may commit frauds and destroy information or they may disclose information to others. This poses a serious trust issue. (Farzad, 2011).

2.1.2. Flooding attack

In this type of attack, attackers can send very large amounts of packets from exploited information resources, and they are called as zombie (innocent host). Here, attacker tries to flood victim by sending huge number of packets from innocent host (*zombies*) in network. Packets can be either one of TCP, ICMP, UDP or a mix of these protocols. These kinds of attacks are mostly realized over unauthorized network connections. Because of cloud computing paradigms' nature, connections to the virtual machines are established everywhere over Internet. For this reason, exposition of cloud users with *Denial of Service (DoS)* and *Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS)* attacks are inevitable. Flooding attacks affect the availability of serviced for authorized users. An attack that is realized to a server which serves one kind of service can prevent a vast of scale accessibility to this served service. These kinds of attacks are called DoS attacks. If servers' resources are slogged after flooding attacks and it prevents the execution of other services, which run on the server, this kind of attacks are called indirect DoS attacks. (Farzad, 2011).

2.1.3. User to Root attacks

In this type of attack, an intruder seizes the account and password information of an authorized user, and he can acquire limitless access to the whole system. This makes him able to exploit vulnerabilities for gaining root level access to system For example; Buffer overflows are used to generate root shells from a process running as root. Buffer overflows are used for establish console connection for authorized processes. This type of intrusion can be realized with writing an excessive amount of data to a statically defined buffers' capacity, and the information is captured by intruders from this overflowed data. An attacker who owned the account and password information of an authorized user can hold the access privilege to servers and also to virtual machines. (Farzad, 2011) and (Laniece, 2013).

2.1.4. Port Scanning

An attack that identifies open, closed and filtered ports on a system. Through port scanning, attackers can find open ports and attack on services running on these ports. Network related details

such as IP address, MAC address, router, gateway filtering, firewall rules etc. can be known through this attack. Various port scanning techniques are TCP scanning, UDP scanning, SYN scanning, FIN scanning, ACK scanning, Window scanning (same as ACK scan but it checks any modifications in the window field of packet) etc. Port scanning is not used by its own, an intruder realize the actual attack after getting information about open ports and running services. (Farzad, 2011).

2.1.5 Attacks on Virtual Machine (VM) or hypervisor

After compromising hypervisor, control of the virtual machines in the virtual environment will be captured. Zero day attacks are one of the methods that attack virtual machines and use hypervisor or other virtual machines to attack other virtual machines. A zeroday vulnerability is a threat that tries to exploit application vulnerabilities that are unknown to others or the software developer. Zero day attacks use known vulnerabilities before system or software developers apply patches or updates. Multiple virtual machines use the same resource pool, especially hardware and with this kind of access side channel data has a chance to be captured, which flow one virtual machine to other. A zero-day vulnerability was exploited in the HyperVM virtualization application which resulted in destruction of many virtual server based websites.

2.1.6. Backdoor channel attacks

It is a passive attack which allows hackers to gain remote access to the infected node in order to compromise user confidentiality. Using backdoor channels, hackers can control victim's resources and can make it as *zombie* to attempt DDoS attack. It can also be used to disclose the confidential data of victim. Due to this, compromised system faces difficulty in performing its regular tasks. In Cloud environment, attacker can get access and control Cloud user's resources through backdoor channel and make VM as *Zombie* to initiate DoS/DDoS attack. For insider attacks, signature based intrusion detection solutions can normally be used. To prevent attacks on VM/Hypervisor, anomaly based intrusion detection techniques can be used. For flooding attack and backdoor channel attack, either signature based intrusion detection or anomaly based intrusion detection techniques can be used. Firewall (in Cloud) could be the common solution to prevent some of the attacks listed above.

2.2 Types of Intrusion Detection in Cloud Computing

Cloud-based IDS can be divided into four types. They shall be described in the following subsections.

2.2.1. Network based IDS

Networks based IDSs (NIDS) capture the traffic of entire network and analyze it to detect possible intrusions like port scanning, DoS attacks etc. NIDS usually performs intrusion detection by processing the IP and transport layer headers of captured network packets. It utilizes the anomaly based and signature based detection methods to identify intrusions. NIDS collects the network packets and looks for their correlation with signatures of known attacks or compares the users' current behavior with their already known profiles in real-time. Multiple hosts in the network can be secured from attackers by utilizing a few properly deployed NIDSs. If run in *stealth* mode, the location of NIDS can be hidden from attacker. The NIDS is unable to perform analysis if traffic is encrypted. In cloud environment, the attacks on hypervisor or VMs are detected by positioning NIDS at the cloud server which interacts with external network. However, it cannot detect attacks inside a virtual network contained by hypervisor. Cloud provider is responsible for installing NIDS in cloud. (Irfan, 2011).

2.2.2. Host based IDS

Hosts based IDSs (HIDS) collect information from a particular host and analyze it to detect intrusive events. The information may be system logs or audit trails of operating system. HIDS analyzes the

information and if there is any change in the behavior of system or program, it reports to network manager that the system is under attack. The effectiveness of HIDS can be improved by specifying the features that provide it more information for detection. However, it requires more storage for information to be analyzed. In the case of cloud computing network, it is possible to deploy HIDS on hypervisor, VM or host to analyze the system logs, user login information or access control policies and detect intrusion events. Cloud user is responsible for supervision of HIDS deployed at a VM while cloud provider is responsible for the deployment of HIDS on hypervisor. HIDS is capable of analyzing encrypted traffic however; it is susceptible to DoS attack and can even be disabled. HIDS are commonly used to protect the integrity of software. (Narwane, 2012).

2.2.3. VMM/Hypervisor based IDS

Hypervisor provides a platform for communication among VMs. Hypervisor based IDSs is deployed at the hypervisor layer. It helps in analysis of available information for detection of anomalous activities. The information is based on communication at various levels like communication between VM and hypervisor, between VMs and communication within the hypervisor based virtual network. (Irfan, 2011).

2.2.4. Distributed IDS

A Distributed IDS (DIDS) comprises numerous IDSs (such as NIDS, HIDS) that are deployed across a large network to monitor the traffic for intrusive behavior. The participant IDSs can communicate with each other or with a centralized server. Each of these individual IDSs has its own two function components: detection component and correlation manager. Detection component monitors the system or subnet and transmits the collected information in a standard format to the correlation manager. Correlation manager combines information from multiple IDS and generates high level alerts that correspond to an attack. Analysis phase makes use of signature based and anomaly based detection methods so DIDS can detect known as well as unknown attacks. In case of cloud, DIDS can be located at any of two positions: at processing server or at host machine. (Irfan, 2011).

3.0 Open source IDS Tools

Open source typically refers to a program whose source code is released for use or modification by the community. Developers are free to download and make changes to the code as they please and create their own personalized product. Some open source IDS tools to review are below.

3.1 Snort: Snort is an open source network intrusion detection system, capable of performing real-time traffic analysis and packet logging on IP networks. It can perform protocol analysis, content searching/matching and can be used to detect a variety of attacks and probes, such as buffer overflows, stealth port scans, CGI attacks, SMB probes, OS fingerprinting attempts, and much more. Through protocol analysis, content searching, and various pre-processors, Snort detects thousands of worms, vulnerability exploit attempts, port scans, and other suspicious behavior. Snort uses a flexible rule-based language to describe traffic that it should collect or pass, and a modular detection engine.

Snort is the hands-down leader in open source NIDS solutions. Though it sports no GUI or easy administration interface, the tool has gained broad acceptance as an effective NIDS solutions for a wide range of scenarios and use cases. Furthermore, various front-ends have been created by the community to address its lack of a GUI. Snort uses both signature-based intrusion detection as well as anomaly-based methods, and can rely on user-created rules or signatures sourced from databases like Emerging Threats. Snort can also use a free Basic Analysis and Security Engine (BASE), a web interface for analyzing its alerts.

Snort can be configured to run in three modes:

- Sniffer mode, which simply reads the packets off of the network and displays them for you in a continuous stream on the console (screen).
- Packet Logger mode, which logs the packets to disk.
- Network Intrusion Detection System (NIDS) mode, which performs detection and analysis on network traffic. This is the most complex and configurable mode.

3.2 Bro IDS: Bro IDS uses anomaly-based intrusion detection, and is usually employed in conjunction with Snort, as the two complement each other quite nicely. Interestingly, Bro is actually a domain-specific language for networking applications in which Bro IDS is written. The technology is especially effective at traffic analysis, and is often used in forensics and related use cases.

Bro, or sometimes referred to as Bro-IDS is a bit different from other tools. In a way Bro is both a signature and anomaly-based IDS. Its analysis engine will convert traffic captured into a series of events. An event could be a user logon to FTP, a connection to a website or practically anything. The power of the system is what comes after the event engine and that's the Policy Script Interpreter. This policy engine has it's own language (Bro-Script) and it can do some very powerful and versatile tasks.

If you're not an analyst then this tool will have a challenging learning curve. Since it was developed as a research tool it didn't initially focus on things like GUIs, usability, and ease of installation. While it does many cool things out of the box many of those things aren't immediately actionable and may be difficult to interpret.

3.3 Suricata: Suricata is a direct competitor to Snort and employs a signature-based methodology, rule/policy driven security, and anomaly-based approach for detecting intrusions. For some, the solution is a modern alternative to the industry standard tool-- a Snort "on steroids," so to speak, with multi-threading capabilities, GPU acceleration, and multiple model statistical anomaly detection, among others.

3.4 Security Onion: Security Onion is actually an Ubuntu-based Linux distribution for IDS and network security monitoring (NSM), and consists of several of the above open-source technologies working in concert with each other. The platform offers comprehensive intrusion detection, network security monitoring, and log management by combining the best of Snort, Suricata, Bro-- as well as other tools such as Sguil, Squert, Snorby, ELSA, Xplico, among others. For those desiring the best of the aforementioned tools in one single package, Security Onion is worth considering.

If one wants to try out one or more of these open source IDS tools, you could save some time and check out Security Onion. It's a distribution of Ubuntu with everything pre-installed.

3.5 OpenWIPS: OpenWIPS despite being logo-less and documentation-less, has created a popular open-source project for wireless security with features and functionality found in comparable solutions costing tens of thousands of dollars. It's signature-based intrusion detection technology consists of sensors to capture wireless traffic, a server to analyze/respond to attacks, and a GUI for easy management.

	Pros	Cons
Snort	Fairly easy to install and get up and running. Vast community of users, many support resources available online.	Comes with no GUI, though community-developed add-ons exist. Packet processing can be slow.
Suricata	Can use Snort's rulesets. Has advanced features such as multi-threading capabilities and GPU acceleration.	Prone to false positives. System and network resource intensive.
Bro IDS	Platform can be tailored for a variety of network security use cases, in addition to NIDS.	Some programming experience is required. Gaining proficiency in Bro DSL can take some effort.
OpenWIPS-ng	Modular and plugin-based. Software and hardware required can be built by DIYers.	Primarily a wireless security solution.
Security Onion	Comprehensive security stack consisting of multiple, leading open-source solutions. Provides an easy setup tool for installing the whole stack.	As a platform made up of several technologies, Security Onion inherits the drawbacks of each constituent tool.

Conclusion

The IDS tools x-rays above are not the only open-source IDS tools available, others include Prelude, Prevx Home, Kismet, OS Tripwire, AIDE etc. This paper described various intrusion threats in a cloud computing environment and briefly discussed some open source IDS tools to detect and prevent intrusion in a cloud computing environment. Security Onion have taken the legwork out of picking/choosing the appropriate tools by combining the most popular open source security tools into one unified solution stack, freely available and easy to install.

References

- A. V. Dastjerdi, K. A. Bakar, S. G. H. Tabatabaei, "Distributed Intrusion Detection in Clouds using Mobile Agents", Third International Conference on Advanced Engineering computing and Applications in Sciences, 2009, pp. 175-180.
- A. Bakshi, Yogesh B, "Securing cloud from DDOS Attacks using Intrusion Detection System in Virtual Machine", 2010 Second International Conference on Communication Software and Networks, pp. 260-264.
- A. Patel, Q. Qassim, Z. Shukor, J. Nogueira, J. Júnior and C. Wills, "Autonomic Agent-Based Self-Managed Intrusion Detection and Prevention System", Proceedings of the South African Information Security Multi-Conference (SAISMC 2010), pp. 223-234.
- Buecker A., Lodewijckx K., Moss H., Skapinetz K., and Waidner M., Cloud Security Guidance IBM Recommendations for the Implementation of Cloud Security, IBM Corp. p. 2, p. 7, p. 19, 2009.
- C. N. Modi, D. R. Patel, A. Patel, R. Muttukrishnan, "Bayesian Classifier and Snort based Network Intrusion Detection System in Cloud Computing", Third International Conference on Computing, Communication and Networking Technologies, 26th-28th July 2012.
- C. Mazzariello, R. Bifulco and R. Canonico, "Integrating a Network IDS into an Open Source Cloud Computing Environment", 2010 Sixth International Conference on Information Assurance and Security, pp. 265-270.
- C. Modi, D. Patel, B. Borisaniya, H. Patel, A. Patel, M. Rajarajan, "A Survey of Intrusion Detection Techniques in Cloud", Journal of Network and Computer Applications 36 (2013), pp. 42-57.
- Chaves D., Aparecida S., Becker Westphall C., and Rodrigo Lamin F., "SLA perspective in security management for cloud computing", International Conference on Networking and Services, IEEE, Mexico, pp. 212-217, 2010.
- Farzad S., "Cloud computing security threats and responses", International Conference on Communication Software and Networks, IEEE, China, pp. 245-249, 2011.
- Foster I., Zhao Y., Raicu I., and Lu S., "Cloud computing and grid computing 360-degree compared", Grid Computing Environments Workshop, IEEE, USA, pp.1-10, 2008.
- Frank Gens. New IDC IT Cloud Services Survey: Top Benefits and Challenges. <http://blogs.idc.com/ie/?p=730>. IDC eXchange, Last viewed (15-10-2016).
- Hai J., Xiang G., Zou D., Wu S., Zhao F., Min Li, and Zheng W., "A VMM-based intrusion prevention system in cloud computing environment", The Journal of Supercomputing, Vo. 66, No. 3, pp. 1133-1151, 2013.
- Hisham A. et al. A Hierarchical Intrusion Detection System for Cloud: Design and Evaluation. International Journal on Cloud Computing Services and Architecture (IJCSA). International Data Corporation, http://blogs.idc.com/ie/wpcontent/uploads/2009/12/idc_cloud_challenges_2009.jpg, 2009. Last viewed (10-10-2016).

<https://www.upguard.com/articles/top-free-network-based-intrusion-detection-systems-ids-for-the-enterprise>. retrieved on 08 - 02-2017.

International Data Corporation, http://blogs.idc.com/ie/wpcontent/uploads/2009/12/idc_cloud_challenges_2009.jpg, 2009. Last viewed (10-10-2016).

J. H. Lee, M. W. Park, J. H. Eom, T. M. Chung, "Multi-level Intrusion Detection System and Log Management in Cloud Computing", ICACT, 2011, pp. 552-555.

J. Han, M. Kamber, "Data Mining: Concepts and Techniques", 2nd edition, Morgan Kaufmann publishers, 2006.

Joe Schreiber (2014): "Open Source Intrusion Detection Tools: A Quick Overview", <https://www.alienvault.com/blogs/security-essentials/open-source-intrusion-detection-tools-a-quick-overview>. retrieved on 08 - 02-2017.

K. Vieira, A. Schuler, Carlos B. Westphall, and C. M. Westphall, "Intrusion Detection for Grid and Cloud Computing", IEEE Computer Society, (July/August 2010), pp. 38-43.

Kaufman L.M., "Data security in the world of cloud computing", IEEE Security & Privacy, Vol. 7, No. 4, pp. 61-64, 2009.

Keiko H., David G. R., Fernández-Medina E., and Fernandez B., "An analysis of security issues for cloud computing", Journal of Internet Services and Applications, Vol. 4, No. 1, pp. 1- 13, 2013.

Kenichi K., and Chiba S., "HyperSpector: Virtual distributed monitoring environments for secure intrusion detection", ACM/USENIX International Conference on Virtual Execution Environments, ACM, USA, pp. 197-207, 2005.

L. M. Ibrahim, "Anomaly Network Intrusion Detection System based on Distributed Time-delay Neural Network", Journal of Engineering Science and Technology, 2010, 5(4), pp. 457-471.

Laniece S., Lacoste M., Kassi-Lahlou M., Bignon F., Lazri K., and Wailly A., "Engineering intrusion prevention services for IaaS clouds: The way of the hypervisor", International Symposium on Service Oriented System Engineering, IEEE, USA, p. 25-36, 2013.

Lo C., Huang C., and Ku J., "A Distributive intrusion prevention system framework for cloud computing networks", International Conference on Parallel Processing Workshops, IEEE, USA, pp. 280-284, 2010.

Ms. P. K. Shelke, Ms. S. Sontakke, Dr. A. D. Gawande, "Intrusion Detection System for Cloud Computing", International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research Volume 1, Issue 4, May 2012, pp. 67-71.

Peter M., and Grance T., The NIST definition of cloud computing (draft), NIST special publication 800 (145), 2011.

Philp Cox (2015), Intrusion detection in a cloud computing environment, <http://searchcloudcomputing.techtarget.com/tip/Intrusion-detection-in-a-cloud-computing-environment> retrieved on 18 - 10-2016

R. Bace, P. Mell, "Intrusion Detection Systems", National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), Technical Report, 800-31, 2001.

- S. Bharadwaja, W. Sun, M. Niamat, F. Shen, "Collabra: A Xen Hypervisor based Collaborative Intrusion Detection System", Eighth International Conference on Information Technology: New Generations, 2011, pp. 695-700.
- S. N. Dhage, B. B. Meshram, R. Rawat, S. Padawe, M. Paingaokar, A. Misra , "Intrusion Detection System in Cloud Computing Environment", International Conference and Workshop on Emerging Trends in Technology (ICWET 2011), pp. 235-239.
- S.V. Narwane, S.L. Vaikol. 2012. Intrusion Detection System in Cloud Computing Environment. In International Conference on Advances in Communication and Computing Technologies (ICACACT).
- Saman Taghavi Z., Takabi H., and James B.D. J., "DCDIDP: A distributed, collaborative, and data-driven intrusion detection and prevention framework for cloud computing environments", International Conference on Collaborative Computing: Networking, Applications and Worksharing, IEEE, USA, pp. 332-341, 2011.
- Saman Taghavi Z., Takabi H., and James B.D. J., "DCDIDP: A distributed, collaborative, and data-driven intrusion detection and prevention framework for cloud computing environments", International Conference on Collaborative Computing: Networking, Applications and Worksharing, IEEE, USA, pp. 332-341, 2011.
- Stiawan D., Abdullah A., and Yazid Idris M., "The trends of intrusion prevention system network", International Conference on Education Technology and Computer, IEEE, China, pp. V4-217-V4-221, 2010.
- Stoneburner G., Goguen A., and Feringa A., Risk management guide for information technology systems, NIST special publication 800.30, 2002.
- U. Oktay, O. K. Sahingoz, "Proxy Network Intrusion Detection System for Cloud Computing", ISBN: 978-1-4673-5613-8, 2013, IEEE, pp. 98-104.
- W. Li, "A Genetic Algorithm Approach to Network Intrusion Detection", SANS Institute, 2004.
- Y. Dhanalakshmi, I. Ramesh Babu, "Intrusion Detection using Data Mining along Fuzzy Logic and Genetic Algorithms", International Journal of Computer Science and Security, 2008, 8(2), pp. 27-32.
- Yassin W., Udzir N. I., Muda, Z., Abdullah A., and Abdullah M. T., "A cloud-based intrusion detection service framework", International Conference on Cyber Security, Cyber Warfare and Digital Forensic, IEEE, Malaysia, pp. 213- 218, 2012.
- Zhi Li 1 ; Yanzhu Liu 1 ; Sujingtao 1 (2015): Third International Conference on Cyberspace Technology (CCT 2015), 2015 page 4 ., Conference: Third International Conference on Cyberspace Technology (CCT 2015)